

Kinetics of solid state reactions under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions

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An attempt has been made to review various theoretical and practical aspects of the kinetics of solid state reactions. A very wide range of models developed so far for the study of the kinetics of such reactions by both isothermal and non-isothermal methods have been documented and their applicability has been critically examined. Though hundreds of literatures are available on this subject, only very relevant ones have been cited to avoid lengthy bibliography.

Chemical compound in solid state can undergo decomposition or combine with another solid compound under the influence of rising temperature forming a product (or one of the products) also in solid state with a structure altogether different from the reactants. In many cases the thermal decomposition of solid is accompanied with the evolution of a gaseous product. Further, such a reaction is either preceded or followed by physical transformation such as melting, sublimation, recrystallization etc. These physical transformations greatly influence the kinetics of solid state reactions as these phenomena are also accompanied with absorption or evolution of heat. Unlike liquid or gas phase reactions, the ions or atoms in the crystal lattice of solid are immobile. The reactivity of a solid depends upon the presence of certain spots or centers which can initiate certain actions to destabilize the stable arrangement of ions/atoms in the lattice under the influence of heat energy. These spots or centers eventually merge together as their number increases or grow to form a zone of enhanced reactivity which advances gradually to the adjoining volume of unreacted material. This reaction zone which serves as interface between reactant and product, advances either from periphery to the center or from center to the surface of a solid volume. This phenomenon of the progress of reaction interface determines the ultimate rate of solid-state reaction. There are several basic tenets¹ on which the kinetics of solid state reaction is based, some of which are as follows :

- (i) The rate of reaction in a solid is proportional to the effective area of the reactant/product interface.
- (ii) The rate of interface advance through an isotropic reactant under isothermal condition is constant.

- (iii) The temperature dependency of most of the solid state reactions obeys Arrhenius equations.
- (iv) Diffusion of one of the product species tends to control the rate if it forms a barrier on the progress of reaction interface.

The above tenets have been formulated on the basis of experimental observations. However, exceptions and anomalous behavior have also been observed. Indeed, heterogeneous reactions are so complex in nature that it is very difficult to make unifying or globally applicable generalizations. The kinetics of heterogeneous, especially solid state reaction has been studied extensively, both theoretically and experimentally. Literature survey will provide hundreds of publications on this topic and their numbers are still growing. The reader is likely to be lost in the deluge of literature without reaping any benefit. Therefore, only very relevant literatures have been cited in this article to avoid unnecessary lengthy bibliography most of which are available in the following monographs : (1) Garner², (2) Hedvall³, (3) Barret⁴, (4) Hannay⁵, (5) Keatch and Dollimore⁶, (6) Brown, Dollimore and Galway¹ (7), Sestak⁷ etc. Besides, the proceedings of the International symposia on "Reactivity of Solids" and on "Thermal Analysis" held every four years provides many important papers on this subject. *Journal of Thermal Analysis* and *Thermochimica Acta* are two important international journals which publishes important research papers on kinetics of solid-state reactions. *Thermochimica Acta* has also published two special issues^{8,9} devoted entirely to the subject in 1973 and 2002.

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Brief comparison between isothermal and non-isothermal methods of study of the kinetics of solid state reactions :

The kinetics of solid state reactions is studied generally by (i) isothermal and by (ii) non-isothermal methods. In earlier literature the isothermal method was mostly employed for study of the kinetics of solid-state reactions. But, during the last three and half decades non-isothermal methods has received more and more attention and as a result, many valuable contributions have been made on this method.

The isothermal method is more accurate and exact if the decomposition reaction is a simple process without any side reactions, such as consecutive or parallel reactions. Since the term concentration has no significance in solid-state reaction the rate is expressed as function of fraction reacted (α) which is determined using either the mass loss/gain data or decrease in surface area or the volume of gas evolved etc. Isothermal α -time plot cannot distinguish any changes in the mechanism during the course of reaction. However, it is possible to distinguish the different steps of reaction by non-isothermal method, especially by DTA and simultaneous TG-DTA or DTG-DTA. Even very minute or subtle change in mechanism can be identified by non-isothermal method by varying the experimental conditions such as heating rate, sample mass, gaseous environment etc.

In determining the kinetic parameters of solid-state reaction by isothermal method several experiments need to be carried out at different temperatures. This is a tardy process. Besides, a perennial problem associated with isothermal method is that certain extent of decomposition takes place before the sample attains the constant temperature of the furnace. This has not yet been solved.

Kinetics of solid-state reaction under isothermal condition

The kinetics of a chemical reaction depends on the slow or rate-determining step. In solid-state reactions the rate-determining step can be either (i) nucleation and growth of product phase or (ii) diffusion, i.e. transportation of reactants/product to, or from the zone of chemical reaction or (iii) chemical reactions at the interface. Intermediate behavior and transition from one rate-controlling regime to another are also observed frequently. Chemical reaction at the interface involves the phenomena of nucleation and growth of the product phase. Nucleation is a process of conversion of reactant into the product phase which grows continuously at the contact between the nucleating particle and the reactant. As the nuclei attain a critical size, growth of product phase begins. However, there is no clear-cut requirement of critical size, which depends mainly on the free en-

ergy of the process sufficient to overcome the barriers to the production of a stable particle of product phase on the crystal surface. On this basis, the following kinetic laws have been considered under nucleation and growth controlled reactions.

Nucleation and growth controlled reaction :

Let us consider the decomposition reaction of the type $A(s) \rightarrow B(s) + C(s)$. If it is assumed that most of the potential embryos are already present in the solid, the entire nucleation process demands only that their development becomes stable. Thus, if N_0 is the total number of such potential embryos in a volume of solid, N is the number of nuclei at any instant t , the rate can be expressed as

$$dN/dt = k_{\beta} (N_0 - N)^{\beta} \quad (1)$$

where, k_{β} is the rate constant for multistep nucleation, β is the number of stages of nucleation. Assuming β as unity, the integrated form of the above equation is given by

$$N = N_0 [1 - \exp(-k_N t)] \quad (2)$$

where, k_N is the single step nucleation. From eqs. (1) and (2) with $\beta = 1$ one obtains

$$dN/dt = k_N N_0 \exp(-k_N t) \quad (3)$$

The exponential term can be expanded up to cubic term as both k_N and t are small

$$dN/dt = k_N N_0 (1 - k_N t + k_N^2 t^2/2 - k_N^3 t^3/6 + \dots) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{If } k_N t \ll 1 \text{ then } dN/dt = k_N N_0, \text{ or, } N = k_N N_0 t \quad (5)$$

which is the linear law of nucleation.

If $k_N t \gg 1$ then $N = N_0$ which signifies that the rate of nucleation is extremely fast i.e. instantaneous. In case of multiple steps of nucleation [see eq. (1)] when $k_{\beta} t \ll 1$ then

$$N_{\beta} = N_0 k_{\beta} t^{\beta} \quad (6)$$

which is the equation for multiple steps of nucleation.

It is difficult to envisage the significance of individual steps involved in the process of nucleation. These steps could be either successive processes in the vicinity of a particular site or the interaction of a several mobile energetic participants in the process, while the product species remain immobilized. Since $N_0 k_{\beta}$ is constant $N_{\beta} = N = k_{\beta} t^{\beta}$ which is the power law of nucleation.

Since nucleation takes place in a fixed volume of reaction product the number of nuclei formed at any time t_j occupy $V(t, t_j)$ volume of product, where t is the time elapsed to initiate nucleation. Thus, we have now two relationships; one relating to the rate of formation of nuclei (eq. (3)) and the other is the rate of growth i.e.

$$V(t) = V(t, t_j) (dN/dt)_{t=t_j} dt_j \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and } V(t, t_j) = \sigma [k_G (t - t_j)]^\lambda \quad (8)$$

where λ is the number of dimensions in which nuclei grow and σ is the shape factor ($4/3\pi$ for spherical nuclei) and k_G is the rate constant for nuclei growth. Suitable combinations of eq. (3) and eq. (7) give the rate expressions for advancement of reaction interface (growth) as well as for different physical phenomena such as power law

$$\alpha = (kt)^n \quad (9)$$

and exponential law

$$V(t) = \alpha = 6\sigma N_0 (k_G/k_N)^3 \{e^{-k_N t} - 1 + k_N t - (k_N t)^2/2 + (k_N t)^3/6 - \dots\} \quad (10)$$

However, the problem becomes more complicated when impingement and ingestion of underdeveloped nuclei are considered. To simplify the problem Avrami (please see Ref. 1) introduced the term $V_{\text{ext}} (= \alpha_E)$ which is defined as the total volume of nuclei including overlapping regions and those growing nuclei which would have formed from ingested nuclei if such situation had occurred in reality. The expression relating α and α_E is as follows :

$$d\alpha/d\alpha_E = 1 - \alpha$$

$$\text{or, } d\alpha_E = d\alpha/(1 - \alpha) = -\ln(1 - \alpha) =$$

$$C(k_G/k_N)^3 \{e^{-k_N t} - 1 + k_N t - (k_N t)^2/2 + \dots\} \quad (11)$$

when both α and t are large the rate process becomes deceleratory and eq. (11) reduces to

$$-\ln(1 - \alpha) = k(k_G t) \quad (12)$$

Johnson and Mehl¹⁰ also arrived at the similar equation as above for nucleation and growth controlled process. Using a different approach Erofeev^{1,7} obtained the following expression

$$-\ln(1 - \alpha) = kt \quad (13)$$

The combined form of eqs. (12) and (13) is therefore known as Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Erofeev equation. Detailed treatment on this topic is available in several standard monographs^{1,5,7,11}. Random nucleation taking place in all directions with resultant branching of chain reaction sometimes leads to extensive surface and bulk deformation. In such case, the rate expression follows exponential law^{12,13} i.e.

$$\alpha = k \exp(k\beta t)$$

$$\text{or, } \ln \alpha = \ln k + k\beta t \quad (14)$$

If the sigmoidal α -time curve is symmetrical in nature i.e. the point of inflection begins from $\alpha = 0.5$, the rate expression for chain branching reaction takes the form as follows

$$d\alpha/dt = k\beta\alpha(1 - \alpha)$$

on integration

$$\ln[\alpha/(1 - \alpha)] = k\beta t + c \quad (15)$$

which is known as the Prout-Tompkin¹⁴ equation applied widely to the decomposition of various crystalline permanganates.

Rate controlled by growth or advancement of reaction interface :

When the nucleation process is rapid and widespread on all surfaces or on a specific crystallographic surface, the kinetics of overall rate process are determined by the geometry of the advancement of reaction interface from surface to the center of the particle. Because of the rapid nucleation process, the induction period, if any, is too short to permit detection and therefore, α -time curve becomes deceleratory even at relatively low value of α . Let us consider a cube of edge a_0 . After a time t the volume of unreacted material (a^3) is equal to $(a_0 - 2k_g t)^3$ where k_g is the growth rate in one direction. Then,

$$\alpha = [a_0^3 - (a_0 - 2k_g t)^3]/a_0^3 = (a_0^3 - a^3)/a_0^3 \quad (16)$$

From eq. (16) it follows that

$$a = a_0(1 - \alpha)^{1/3} \quad (17)$$

and

$$a_0 - 2k_g t = a_0(1 - \alpha)^{1/3} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{or } 1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3} = kt \quad (19)$$

where, $k = 2k_g/a_0$

Similarly, if after time t , the unreacted core of a sphere is r then

$$r_0 - r = k't/\rho \quad (20)$$

where, r_0 and ρ represent initial radius and density respectively of the reactant. If W_0 and W represent initial and final weight of reactant respectively then $a = (W_0 - W)/W_0$. Therefore,

$$\frac{W}{W_0} = 1 - \alpha = \left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^3 \quad (21)$$

Combining eqs. (20) and (21) one can arrive at the following equation

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3} = k't/\rho r_0 \quad (22)$$

This is often referred to as the contracting volume model in solid-state reaction.

The above geometrical approach to derive the rate of progress of the reaction interface can be further generalized if we consider a rectangular parallelepiped of sides a , b and c allowing reactions to occur at different planar surfaces. For such a geometry the fraction reacted may be expressed as¹

$$\alpha = \frac{abc - (a - 2k_a t)(b - 2k_b t)(c - 2k_c t)}{abc} \quad (23)$$

where k_a , k_b and k_c are the rates of interface advance in three crystallographic directions. When $a = b \gg c$ and $k_a = k_b = k_c$, the diminution in dimension of the particle of unreacted solid is small in the direction of a ($\gg 2k_a t$) and b ($\gg 2k_b t$). With these assumptions eq. (23) reduces to the following

$$\alpha = 2k_c t / c \quad (24)$$

which explains a zero order reaction taking place on thin disc or plate like particles where no effective decrease in area is observed, i.e. where interface advance is independent of the area of the reacting surface.

Similar considerations of a reaction where $a \gg b = c$ and $k_a = k_b = k_c$, it can be shown that

$$\alpha = \frac{abc - a(b - 2k_b t)(c - 2k_c t)}{abc} \quad (25)$$

Since the change in the dimension of a -axis is negligibly small and $b = c$ we have

$$\alpha = 1 - \left[\frac{b - 2k_b t}{b} \right]^2 \quad (26)$$

On simplification of the above expression, we have

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/2} = \left(\frac{2k_b}{b} \right) t \quad (27)$$

The above equation is also known as contracting area model and has been found to be applicable in the case of dehydration of layer type lattice. The same equation can be obtained for a long cylindrical particle ($l \gg r$) so that change takes place in two dimension only. Therefore, advancing reaction zone or boundary in a crystalline solid can be expressed by the following general equation.

$$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/n} = kt \quad (28)$$

where n is the number of dimensions (3, 2 and 1) in which the interface advances.

Diffusion-controlled reactions :

In a diffusion-controlled reaction, the overall rate is determined by the movement of one or more reactant species to, or a product from the reaction interface; alternatively, heat transfer may be important. Decomposition of solids is not usually controlled by mass transfer processes except for certain reversible reactions or where large heat changes take place. Wherever such a rate-controlling mechanism exists in solid-state reaction, careful experimentation is necessary to eliminate occurrence of other rate-limiting steps. Since the formation of a barrier layer diminishes the effective contact between reactants, the nucleation step is very

rapid in the range of temperature used. As a result, the α -time plots are often deceleratory throughout the reaction regime. In addition to the gradual diminution in rate as a result of increase in thickness of barrier layer, the kinetic characteristics are also changed according to the geometry of the solid reactant.

If the area of the reacting surface remains constant during the reaction, the decrease in rate constant is a consequence of the increase in thickness of the barrier layer over that surface. The simplest rate law is expressed as follows :

$$\alpha = (k_1 t)^{1/2} \quad (29)$$

The above expression which is also known as parabolic rate law has been found to obey the rate of oxidation of metal plates or discs^{15,16}. The rate expression for two-dimensional diffusion with cylindrical symmetry, i.e. from the center of the cylinder to its periphery is :

$$(1 - \alpha) \ln(1 - \alpha) + \alpha = \frac{k_2 t}{r^2} \quad (30)$$

A diffusion limited reaction proceeding in a spherical particle of radius r obeys a rate expression obtained by combining eqs. (22) and (29),

$$\left[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3} \right]^2 = \frac{2k_3 D t}{r^2} \quad (31)$$

where D is the coefficient of diffusion of one species in to the other. This equation is followed when one of the reactants (A) is completely surrounded by other reactant (B). The product grows through diffusion from the center to the periphery of A. Eq. (31) is known as the Jander's equation¹⁷.

Jander's equation, in many heterogeneous reactions, follows only in the initial stage (0–30%) of the reaction and large deviation is observed at higher conversion of α . This may be due to the following reasons.

- (i) Eq. (29) is valid for a planar surface whose area is very large compared to the thickness of the product layer.
- (ii) On the other hand, eq. (31) is valid when the volume of the unreacted core plus the volume of the reaction product is equal to the volume of the original material, i.e. there is no change in volume. But, such an approximation is rarely valid for the entire course of reaction.

Expanding the square term on the L.H.S. of eq. (31) and incorporating necessary simplifications, Ginstling and Braunshtein¹⁸ obtained the following equation

$$1 - \frac{2}{3}\alpha - (1 - \alpha)^{2/3} = \frac{k_4Dt}{r^2} \quad (32)$$

Some of the anomalies of Jander's equation are eliminated in the above equation so that it follows over a wide range of α . Carter and Valensi^{19,20} modified eq. (32) when the molar volume of product is different from that of the reactant. The modified equation is as follows :

$$[1 + (z - 1)\alpha]^{2/3} + (z - 1)(1 - \alpha)^{2/3} = z + 2(1 - z) \frac{k_5Dt}{r^2} \quad (33)$$

where z is the ratio between the corresponding molar volumes of reactant and product. Eq. (33) is considered as the exact form of diffusion and reduces to eq. (32) when $z = 1$. Zhuravlev *et al.*²¹ have postulated that the rate of interface advance under diffusion-controlled reaction is also proportional to the fraction of unreacted substance $(1 - \alpha)$ present and assuming a contracting sphere of radius r , they obtained the following relationship.

$$[(1 - \alpha)^{-1/2} - 1]^2 = \frac{2k_6Dt}{r^2} \quad (34)$$

Komatsu²² has put forward the hypothesis that the reaction in many powder mixtures is initiated only at interparticle contact zone and that the product formation occurs by diffusion through these contact zones. One of the participating reactants is not covered with a coherent product layer. As a result, diffusion takes place from the core to the growing product layer. Quantitative consideration of the model leads to the anti-Jander equation

$$[(1 + \alpha)^{-1/2} - 1]^2 = \frac{2k_7Dt}{r^2} \quad (35)$$

Selection of appropriate model for the kinetic analysis of isothermal solid-state reaction

Table 1 summarizes different possible kinetic models which find application in various types of heterogeneous reactions. These model equations have been suitably coded and these codes are now universally accepted by the thermochemists. However, there may be instances where individual authors have used their own codes in the case of certain uncommon models.

The purpose of kinetic studies is to obtain information concerned on the reaction mechanism through comparison of a series of measured values (α , t) and the functional relationship between α and t which have been derived from model given in the Table 1. Most methods of analysis are based on determining which model in Table 1 provides the best linear fit to the experimental data. Obedience to particular relationship is then consistent with but not the only proof of the reaction model used.

Such a proposition needs to be supported by other independent evidence such as microscopic observations. However, the following sources of error must be sorted out before any attempt to derive meaningful kinetic information from the α -time curve is made.

- (i) α must be meaningfully defined and capable of accurate measurement.
- (ii) Error in the measurement of the final yield distorts the α -time curve. Accurate determination of final product yield in the isothermal method is a major experimental difficulty frequently confronted with.
- (iii) The composition of product may vary with α .
- (iv) Enthalpy change during reaction, especially due to melting or phase change may cause local and/or temporary deviations from the isothermal condition.

Table 1. Some important mechanistic equations (models) used in the study of the kinetics of solid-state reactions

Model (code)	Name of model equations	Equations in their integrated form, $g(\alpha)$	Equations in their differential forms, $f(\alpha)$
Diffusion-controlled models :			
D1	(i) One dimensional	α^2	$1/2\alpha$
D2	(ii) Two dimensional	$(1 - \alpha) \ln(1 - \alpha) + \alpha$	$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{-1}$
D3	(iii) Three dimensional (Jander's equation)	$[1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]^2$	$3/2(1 - \alpha)^{2/3} [1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/3}]^{-1}$
D4	(iv) Three dimensional (Ginshtling and Braunshtein eqn.)	$1 - 2/3\alpha - (1 - \alpha)^{2/3}$	$3/2[(1 - \alpha)^{-1/3} - 1]^{-1}$
AJ	(v) Anti-Jander (Komatsu) equation	$[(1 + \alpha)^{1/2} - 1]^2$	$3/2(1 + \alpha)^{2/3} [(1 + \alpha)^{1/3} - 1]^{-1}$
ZLT	(vi) Zuravlev, Lesokhin and Tempelman equation	$[(1 - \alpha)^{-1/2} - 1]^2$	$3/2(1 + \alpha)^{4/3} [(1 + \alpha)^{1/3} - 1]^{-1}$
Nucleation and growth controlled models :			
Am	(i) Avrami-Erofee'v equation with $m = 1.5, 2, 3$ and 4	$[-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^{1/m}$	$m(1 - \alpha)[- \ln(1 - \alpha)]^{(m-1)/m}$
FI	(ii) First order reaction (Random nucleation)	$-\ln(1 - \alpha)$	$1 - \alpha$
Rn	Contracting phase boundary	$1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1/n}$	$n(1 - \alpha)^{(n-1)/n}$
	(i) Spherical geometry ($n = 3$)		
	(ii) Cylindrical geometry ($n = 2$)		

- (v) Kinetic behavior may change during the course of reaction.
- (vi) Rate equations are often found to vary with pretreatment of the reactants.
- (vii) The influence of grain size distribution of the reacting substance is significant in many solid-state reactions.

Having taken the necessary precautions to obtain the required α -time curve at different temperatures, it is now the task to identify the kinetic model for the reaction. The following procedures¹ are generally used.

- (i) Testing of the best linearity of a plot of $g(\alpha)$ against time (as judged by the highest value of the square of correlation coefficient). The slope value is the rate-constant for the overall reaction.
- (ii) Comparison of the slope of α vs reduced time (t /time to reach certain value of α) plot with the calculated curves for various kinetic models (Table 1) for which tabulated data are available in literature⁶.
- (iii) Comparison of the measured $d\alpha/dt$ vs α value with master curves. However, this procedure requires accurate values of α .
- (iv) Comparison of the measured $d\alpha/dt$ vs reduced time which may facilitate the discrimination between alternative kinetic obediences.

Where versatile computer software is available, procedure (i) is sufficient to discriminate between different models. Though the procedure (ii) has been used by many authors, its disadvantages have been discussed by Keatch and Dollimore⁶, Sharp *et al.*²³, Geiss²⁴ mainly due to the fact that it involves the comparison with a curve which is subjected to various procedural inaccuracies.

More than three decades ago Sestak and Berggren²⁵ proposed the following empirical model combining the different rate-controlling processes :

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n [-\ln(1 - \alpha)]^r \quad (36)$$

Further mathematical analysis²⁶ of the above equation has shown that no more than two kinetic exponents are generally necessary to analyse the data. Therefore, eliminating the third term eq. (36) takes the following form :

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (37)$$

If the exponent m is set equal to zero, the remaining exponent n is the order of the reaction. However, Sestak-Berggren model has been found to be inadequate for describing the generalized form of the kinetics of heterogeneous reaction²⁷.

An alternative method is to make a log-log plot of the experimental data according to the following equation.

$$\ln [-\ln(1 - \alpha)] = n \ln t + \text{constant} \quad (38)$$

From the magnitude of the value of n , it may be possible to obtain an idea about the mechanism of reaction. As for example, values of n for diffusion-controlled reactions are usually between 0.53 and 0.58; for the contracting geometry are 1.04–1.08 and for the Johnson-Mehl-Avrami-Erof'eev equation are 2.0–4.0. However, the important problem of this method is the insensitivity of the double logarithmic plot which on many occasions yield meaningless values of n . Jones *et al.*²⁸ have provided an alternative approach to the linearization of data using the reduced time values of Sharp *et al.*²³. Brown *et al.*²⁹ have used various test procedures as described above for the kinetics of dehydration of $\text{LiSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Kinetics of solid-state reactions under non-isothermal conditions

So far we have discussed isothermal method of studying of kinetics of solid-state reactions which may also be investigated under non-isothermal condition. Consequently, all the thermal effects in a certain range of temperature can be studied from a single experimental run. Although close agreement in the Arrhenius parameters between isothermal and non-isothermal methods has been reported^{30–33}, for a large number of decomposition reactions, especially for reversible reactions, agreement has been far less satisfactory.

In the beginning of the article advantages and limitations of non-isothermal method have been briefly discussed. Apart from general applicability of the Arrhenius type of equation in solid-state kinetics, the criteria for the applicability of mechanistic models proposed originally for isothermal reactions to non-isothermal technique have been questioned. However, the crux of all these issues lies in the experimental accuracy and the way the results are interpreted. Errors attributable to heat transfer during endo or exothermic processes and/or concurrent removal of volatile products in reversible reactions are of great importance in non-isothermal kinetics. The material in direct contact with the container is at higher temperature than that within the bulk mass and such differences are more pronounced in case of reversible reactions. Non-isothermal kinetics are also affected by gaseous environment, heating rate, crucible geometry etc. These effects can be minimized but cannot be completely eliminated.

Mathematical formulation of non-isothermal method

The generalized kinetic expression for non-isothermal method is based on the three basic equations.

- (i) Linear rate of heating, i.e. $dT/dt = b$.
- (ii) The Arrhenius equation, $k = A \exp(-E/RT)$ where, k = sp. rate constant.
- (iii) A suitable rate expression for the function of α , i.e. $d\alpha/dt = kf(\alpha)$.

Combination of the above three equations (which again is not beyond debate) gives the following kinetic equation :

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \frac{A}{b} \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (39)$$

There are several methods for deriving kinetic parameters from eq. (39). These are :

- (1) Differential method, i.e. direct application of eq. (39).
- (2) Difference-differential method, e.g. Freeman and Carroll method.
- (3) Integral method. This method consists of either of the following :
 - (i) Method using a simple approximation of the exponential temperature integral.
 - (ii) Method using a series expansion of the exponential temperature integral.
 - (iii) Method involving integration with respect to a reference temperature.
- (4) Model independent method based on heating rate such as,
 - (i) Friedmann method.
 - (ii) Ozawa-Flynn-Wall method.
 - (iii) Kissinger method.

Each of the above methods will now be discussed separately.

Differential method

The generalized rate eq. (39) may be expressed in the logarithmic form as follows :

$$\ln \left[\frac{d\alpha/dT}{f(\alpha)} \right] = \ln \left(\frac{A}{b} \right) - \frac{E}{RT} \quad (40)$$

Thus, a plot of L.H.S. against $1/T$ yields both E and A from the slope and intercept respectively if the correct form of $f(\alpha)$ is known³⁴⁻³⁶. A list of $f(\alpha)$ expressions used commonly in solid state reactions is given in Table 1. The accuracy of $d\alpha/dT$ measurement is increased if the number of observations, say about ten from either side of the mean temperature and a polynomial curve fitting are used. For order-based models i.e. $(1 - \alpha)^n$ the value of n has to be determined by independent methods such as those proposed by Horowitz and Metzger³⁷ and Gulyai and Greenhow³⁸. The corresponding relationships are given below :

$$1 - \alpha_{\max} = n^{1/(1-n)} \quad (41)$$

$$1 - \alpha_{\max} = 1.062 n^{1/(1-n)} \quad (42)$$

where α_{\max} is the fraction reacted at the maximum rate of decomposition. The best way is to draw a master curve between n and different α_{\max} values using the above relationships. From the master curves n can be obtained for known values of α_{\max} . A less accurate method is the determination of shape index(s) of a DTA peak from which n can be obtained³⁹. The shape indices of different types of DTA peaks have been illustrated in Ref. 39.

$$n = 1.26 s^{1/2} \quad (43)$$

The main objection to this method is the ambiguity in the determination of the shape index of the DTA peak which for many reactions does not have either well-defined base line or inflection points. Another objection to the differential method is the suppression/insensitiveness of experimental errors due to the logarithmic form of $d\alpha/dT$.

Difference-differential method

This method was first proposed by Freeman and Carroll⁴⁰ and the equation derived by them from the TG curve using $f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n$ is given below.

$$\Delta \log \frac{d\alpha}{d\tau} = n\Delta \log (1 - \alpha) - \frac{E}{2.3R} \Delta (1/T) \quad (44)$$

Rearranging, the above equation may be written as

$$\frac{\Delta \log (d\alpha/dT)}{\Delta \log (1 - \alpha)} = \frac{E}{2.3R} \left\{ \frac{\Delta (1/T)}{\Delta \log (1 - \alpha)} \right\} + n \quad (45)$$

Though this equation has been widely used by numerous investigators for the determination of kinetic parameters of solid state reactions it has been subject to criticism very often. Second, differentiation of the logarithmic value of derivatives not only eliminates evaluation of data both at high and low conversions, but also brings about considerable inaccuracy in the region of maximum rate of decomposition. Though several remedial methods have been suggested⁴¹ kinetic parameters are only procedural depending upon the method of calculation employed.

Integral method

The method is based on the integration of basic differential eq. (39) under non-isothermal condition as shown below.

$$\int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = g(\alpha) = \frac{A}{b} \int_{T_0}^T \exp(-E/RT) dT \quad (46)$$

$$\text{or, } g(\alpha) = \frac{AE}{bR} \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-x}}{x^2} dx \quad (47)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is the integrated forms of various kinetic model equations as given in Table 1 and $x = E/RT$. Integrating by

parts and introducing a new function $p(x)$ for the negative exponential integral of temperature function under the condition that if T_0 is selected before the initiation of the reaction. then $p(x_0)$ is negligibly small. Hence, eq. (47) may be written as follows.

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{AE}{bR} p(x) \quad (48)$$

This is known as Doyle's^{42,43} equation. Taking logarithm on both sides,

$$\log g(\alpha) = \frac{AE}{bR} + \log p(x) \quad (49)$$

$$\text{or, } \log g(\alpha) - \log p(x) = \text{constant} = B \quad (50)$$

Zsako⁴⁴ utilized the magnitude of the constancy of B by using statistical method. According to this method for an assumed model the E value is varied keeping the value of A constant. This leads to change in $\log p(x)$ values and therefore B values also. This process is repeated for different models until a minimum value of standard deviation δ is obtained for a particular model from the following equation.

$$\delta = \left[\frac{\sum (Bi - \bar{B})^2}{M} \right]^{1/2} \quad (51)$$

where Bi stands B values calculated from a single point in TG curve, \bar{B} is the arithmetic mean of individual Bi values and M represents the number of experimental points. Zsako and Zsako⁴⁵ subsequently used double minimization of standard deviation as follows.

$$Dm = \left[\frac{\sum (Bi - \bar{B})^2}{MB^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (52)$$

However, many authors have made attempts to determine the value of $p(x)$, using both approximate and series expansion methods. These are discussed below.

Approximation of $p(x)$ function :

Doyle⁴² has shown that the plot of $\log p(x)$ vs $1/T$ in the range of $20 < x < 60$ is essentially linear and obeys the following empirical relationship :

$$\log p(x) = -2.315 - 0.4567 E/RT \quad (53)$$

Combining with eq. (49) one gets

$$\log g(\alpha) = \log \frac{AE}{bR} - 2.315 - 0.4567 E/RT \quad (54)$$

However, at lower values of x ($15 < x < 35$), the following relationship is found to hold better.

$$\log p(x) = -2.0 - 0.4667 E/RT \quad (55)$$

MacCallum and Tanner⁴⁶ extending the above argument of

Doyle have shown that the slope X and intercept a of the linear relationship between $\log p(x)$ and $1/T$ are related to activation energy as follows.

$$-X = bE^c \quad (56)$$

$$\text{and } a = y + bE \quad (57)$$

Determining these constants of the above two equations analytically, MacCallum and Tanner⁴⁶ have obtained the following empirical relationship :

$$\log p(x) = -0.4828E^{0.435} - \left[\frac{0.449 + 0.2117E}{T} \right] x 10^3 \quad (58)$$

where E is the activation energy (in kcal) and T is the temperature in K. Combining eqs. (49) and (58)

$$\log g(\alpha) = \log \frac{AE}{bR} - 0.4828E^{0.435} - \left[\frac{0.449 + 0.2117E}{T} \right] x 10^3 \quad (59)$$

Thus the slope ($tg\beta$) of the plot of $\log g(\alpha)$ vs $1/T$ gives

$$tg\beta = -(0.449 + 0.2117E)x 10^3 \quad (60)$$

from which the value of E can be calculated. Criado and Ortega⁴⁷ have argued that for low values of x , instead of $\log p(x)$ vs $1/T$, a better linear relationship is obtained from the plot of $\log [g(x)/T^{1.8}]$ vs $1/T$ and following similar procedure as followed by MacCallum and Tanner, they have obtained the following relationship.

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^{1.8}} \right] = \log \left[\frac{9.3 x 10^{-6} AE^{-0.876}}{bR} \right] - \left[\frac{14.16 x 218.8E}{T} \right] \quad (61)$$

Madhusudanan *et al.*⁴⁸ using the first six term of the Schlomilch series to determine $p(x)$ values, have found that $\ln p(x)$ is a linear function of x . The slope and the intercept values for such plots are also found to be linear function of $1/x$ and $\ln x$ respectively. Combining these relationships they obtained

$$\ln p(x) = \alpha + bx + c \ln x \quad (62)$$

Substituting the numerical values of a , b and c determined analytically and introducing $\log p(x)$ function in the generalized Doyle's equation (eq. (48)) the authors obtained the following empirical relationship.

$$\ln \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^{1.9215}} \right] = \ln \frac{AE}{bR} + 0.37721 - 1.9215 \ln E - \frac{0.1204E}{T} \quad (63)$$

In the approximation method of determining $p(x)$, a significant contribution has been made by Coats and Redfern⁴⁹ using the following approximation of $p(x)$, i.e.

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x^2} \left[1 - \frac{2}{x} \right] \quad (64)$$

Using this $p(x)$ function the authors derived the following well-known relationship

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \log \frac{AR}{bE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (65)$$

Eq. (65) gives an error of about 10% for $x < 10$. Subsequently various authors have suggested modifications with an objective to reduce the extent of error at lower values of x . Thus, Gorbachev⁵⁰ used the first term of Schlömilch series to obtain the $p(x)$ values from the following relationship.

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x^2} \left[\frac{1}{1+2x} \right] \quad (66)$$

From this relationship it can be shown that

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \log \left[\frac{AR}{bE} \right] + \left[\frac{1}{1+(2E/RT)} \right] - \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (67)$$

Balarin⁵¹ has proposed the following relationship for $p(x)$ function

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x^2} \left[1 + \frac{4}{x} \right]^{-1/2} \quad (68)$$

from which the following relationship was derived

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \log \frac{AR}{bE} - \frac{1}{2} \log \left[1 + \frac{4RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (69)$$

Similarly, Li⁵² has suggested the following equation

$$\log \left[\frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \log \left[\frac{AR}{bE} \right] + \log \left[\frac{1-2RT/E}{1-6(RT/E)^2} \right] - \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (70)$$

Agrawal⁵³ has shown that most of the approximations of $p(x)$ value can be generalized by the following form

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x^2} \left[\frac{1-2/x}{1-m(1/x)^2} \right] \quad (71)$$

where, $m = 0, 4$ and 6 in eqs. (65), (67) and (70) respectively. Agrawal^{53,54} has shown that deviation from each of the above equations from the true value of $p(x)$ is much higher when m is assumed to be any of the above values. However, putting $m = 5$, he has found minimum deviation from the theoretical value of $p(x)$. Therefore, eq. (71) is now being gradually accepted as a more correct form of $p(x)$ approximation⁵⁵.

Methods based on series expansion of the $p(x)$ function :

The $p(x)$ function values can also be evaluated by using both convergent and semi-convergent series for negative exponential integral $[Ei(-x)]$ valid for different ranges of x . Some of the commonly used series expressions are as fol-

lows⁸ :

(1) For $x > 10$ using Taylor's series (convergent)

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x} \left[0.577 + \ln x - x + \frac{x^2}{2.2!} - \dots + \frac{(-1)^n x^n}{n, n!} \right] \quad (72)$$

(2) For $x > 16$ using integration by parts (semi-convergent)

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x} \left[1 - \frac{2!}{x} + \frac{3!}{x^2} - \dots + \frac{(-1)^n (n+1)!}{x^n} \right] \quad (73)$$

(3) For $x > 15$ according to Schlömilch's semi-convergent series

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x(x+1)} \left[1 - \frac{1}{x+2} + \frac{1}{(x+2)(x-3)} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^{n+1} a_n}{(x+2)(x+3)\dots(x+n)} \right] \quad (74)$$

where, a_n is a specific constant. Since $Ei(-x)$ is an asymptotic or non-convergent function, use of expression (72) will introduce larger error than expression (73). Expression (74) is, however, found to be most suitable. Senum and Yang⁵⁶ proposed the following relationship for $p(x)$ function which is claimed to have error lower than 10^{-5} percent for $10 < x < 100$.

$$p(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x} \frac{x^3 + 18x^2 + 88x + 96}{x^4 + 20x^3 + 120x^2 + 240x + 120} \quad (75)$$

Urbanovici and Segal⁵⁷ have proposed several approximate relationships for the calculation of $p(x)$, especially for small temperature range. Though very few authors have used more than four or five terms of any of the above series, it is suggested that in this age of modern computing facilities, precise determination of $p(x)$ is possible by taking into account more number of terms in the calculation. Future investigations are likely to be focused in this direction.

Methods involving integration with respect to a reference temperature :

The main objective of this method is to avoid complicated integration of negative exponential term using a reference temperature such as temperature of DTA and DTG peaks or the temperatures of inflection of DTA and TG traces. Van Krevelen *et al.*⁵⁸ were the first to make an attempt in this direction, but because of certain unrealistic and complex assumptions on which the equation was developed, the method has been scarcely used.

An important contribution in the use of reference temperature in kinetic analysis of solid-state reaction is the method suggested by Horowitz and Metzger³⁷. In order to avoid the constant of integration obtained on integrating eq.

(39) the author used a characteristic temperature ϕ , defined as $\phi = T - T_m$ where T_m is the temperature at the maximum rate of decomposition. Thus integrating the exponential temperature function from T to T_m the authors obtained

$$\ln [1 - (1 - \alpha)^{1-n}] = \ln (1 - n) + \frac{E\phi}{RT_m^2} \text{ when } n \neq 1 \quad (76)$$

$$\ln [-\ln (1 - \alpha)] + \frac{E\phi}{RT_m^2} \text{ when } n = 1 \quad (77)$$

From the slope value of the plot of L.H.S. vs ϕ , E value can be obtained. Dharwadkar and Karkhanawala⁵⁹ have pointed out that the inflection temperature (T_i) and consequently T_m varies with sample size and the heating rate which do not allow the temperature to be representative of the sample. Due to self-cooling, the temperature deviation from the true value is at maximum just when the reaction rate reaches its maximum. Therefore, inflection point they proposed is a temperature of inception of the process, i.e. T_i ($T = T_i + \phi$) and derived the following modified first order equation.

$$\log [-\ln(1 - \alpha)] = \frac{E}{2.3RT_i^2} - \frac{100\phi}{T_i - T_i} + C \quad (78)$$

where T_i is temperature of termination of the process and C is the integration constant. However, Kanungo⁶⁰ has shown that the temperature correction term on the right hand side of eq. (78) is not applicable to the thermal decomposition characteristics of $Mg(OH)_2$ prepared under different conditions. Doyle⁶¹ has however used the modified form of Horowitz and Metzger equation assuming that for any decomposing substance $\log g(\alpha_m)$ is a constant quantity and therefore, a constant term will appear in eq. (77).

Model independent methods involving variable heating rates

Many of the methods discussed in the preceding sections for determining kinetic parameters have been subjected to criticism time and again because of two main reasons. These are : (i) The parameters are frequently determined from a single TA curve at a fixed heating rate. Under this condition any multistep process or any change in mechanism during the course of reaction can not be detected. (ii) The methods require a prior knowledge of mechanism which, in most cases, is rather impossible to obtain. All these aspects have been discussed in detail by Flynn⁶². The isoconversion method is therefore increasingly followed for the study of the kinetics of solid state reaction. Broadly, there are two methods under this heading.

(1) Isoconversion method of Ozawa, Flynn and Wall (OFW).

(2) Change in the temperature of maximum conversion with heating rate.

Besides these two methods Friedman's isoconversion rate method is a corollary of method (1) and therefore is not considered as a separate method.

Isoconversion method of OFW :

This method was developed independently by Ozawa⁶³ in Japan and Flynn and Wall⁶⁴ in USA. According to this method, if the reaction mechanism does not undergo any change over a range of α (or temperature) during the course of reaction then eq. (49) is valid at different heating rates. In the absence of any exact solution for $p(x)$ we may use the following Doyle's⁴² approximation when $20 < x < 60$. (eq. (53))

$$p(x) = -2.315 - 0.4567 x$$

Substituting in eq. (49) and rearranging

$$\log b = \log \left[\frac{AE}{Rg(\alpha)} \right] - 2.315 - 0.4567 \left(\frac{E}{RT} \right) \quad (79)$$

Therefore, plot of $\log b$ vs $1/T$ should yield a series of straight lines for different values of α taken at suitable regular intervals. The E values obtained by this method are independent of any mechanistic model. If the decomposition takes place without any large variation in E value for a wide range of α , then a uniformly similar mechanism is assumed to be operative. However, large change in E value with increasing degree of conversion indicates a complex reaction mechanism. Such large variation takes place when the overall reaction consists of several competitive or parallel reactions. Ozawa⁶³ also introduced the concept of reduced time θ which is given by

$$\theta = (E/bR).p(x) \quad (80)$$

Substituting in eq. (49) we get $g(\alpha) = A\theta$. This shows that goodness of the fit of the plot of $g(\alpha)$ vs θ itself provides an opportunity to identify the appropriate mechanism involved in the process. To calculate θ , $p(x)$ in eq. (80) is substituted by the Doyle's approximation (eq. (53)) and taking logarithm we obtain

$$\log \theta = \log \frac{E}{bR} - 2.315 - 0.4567 \left(\frac{E}{RT} \right) \quad (81)$$

The E value used in this case is the average of individual E values obtained from the linear plots of $\log b$ vs $1/T$ at different conversion levels (α). By using the average E value $\log \theta$ (or θ) values at different temperatures (i.e. corresponding α) are calculated for a given heating rate. Similarly, θ values obtained for at least three heating rates are averaged to obtain mean θ at different values of α . Friedman's⁶⁵ analysis is based on similar arguments, but uses the following equation.

$$\log \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \log f(\alpha) + \log A - \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (82)$$

For a fixed degree of conversion the plots of $\log(d\alpha/dt)$ vs $1/T$ give straight lines from which E can be calculated. However, OFW method is more reliable than that of Friedman's method.

Kissinger's method :

Kissinger³⁹ has shown that for a simple first order decomposition reaction the temperature at the maximum rate of decomposition (T_m) varies with heating rate. Subsequently, it has been shown⁶⁶ that the proposition is also valid when $n \neq 1$. The procedure followed by the author was double differentiation of the generalized non-isothermal equation (eq. (39)) and set the condition $d^2\alpha/dt^2 = 0$. The relationships obtained are as follows :

When $n = 1$

$$\log \left(\frac{b}{T_m^2} \right) = \log \frac{AR}{E} - \frac{E}{2.3RT_m} \quad (83)$$

and when $n \neq 1$

$$\log \left(\frac{b}{T_m^2} \right) = \log \left[\left(\frac{AR}{E} \right) - n(1 - \alpha_m)^{n-1} \right] = \frac{E}{2.3RT} \quad (84)$$

The above relationship may also be derived by using the most approximate solution of $p(x)$ i.e. $p(x) = \exp(-x)/x^2$ for $50 > x > 20$. Substituting this approximate solution of $p(x)$ into eq. (49) a relationship similar to eq. (83) can be obtained. The order of the reaction (n) was determined by Kissinger using the following equation.

$$(1 - \alpha_m) = n^{1/(1-n)} \quad (85)$$

where, α_m is the fraction reacted at T_m . Various ramifications of this method and its application in different aspects of thermal analysis have been studied by different authors^{67,68}. According to them, many useful kinetic information can be obtained if Kissinger's method is applied judiciously in the case of DTA, DTG, DSC and even TPD (temperature programmed desorption).

Transformation of non-isothermal to isothermal rate process :

By definition, for an isothermal process the reduced time θ can also be expressed as follows⁶³

$$\theta = \int \exp \left(\frac{-E}{RT} \right) dt \quad (86)$$

Differentiating and combining with Arrhenius equation

$$d\theta/dt = k/A = \text{constant} \quad (87)$$

$$\text{or, } \theta = (k/A)t \quad (88)$$

where, k = specific rate constant. Since for an isothermal

process T is constant we may reinvoke Arrhenius equation to obtain the following transformation.

$$\theta = \exp(-E/RT_{iso})t \quad (89)$$

Taking logarithm and rearranging

$$\log t = \log \theta + (E/2.303 RT_{iso}) \quad (90)$$

From eq. (90) one can calculate time elapsed to reach different conversion levels (α) at a constant temperature (T_{iso}) by using mean θ values. The far-reaching importance of determining Arrhenius parameters by the isoconversion method and its predictive capability beyond the experimental range have been discussed by Vyazovkin and Lesnikovich^{69,70}.

Problems involved in deriving meaningful kinetic data for solid-state reactions by thermo-analytical method

The discussion on the above subject was initiated about twenty years ago by a group of well-known thermoanalytical chemists at the VIIIth ICTA held at Bratislava (1985) and subsequently continued in several international fora. Since then many papers dealing with this hotly debated subject, i.e. usefulness of kinetic data in solid-state reactions appeared in both *Journal of Thermal Analysis* and *Thermochimica Acta* during late eighties and early nineties. As a consequence, an International Committee was formed under the Chairmanship of Prof. J. H. Flynn to go through the various aspects of the subject and to recommend the norms of standard for future studies on solid-state reaction kinetics. The debate is centered on two points : (1) Adequacy of the so-called models to describe the heterogeneous phase reactions, especially for a multiparticle system. (2) Apparent lack of physical significance of kinetic parameters derived from the Arrhenius equation. These two major sources of controversy are examined below taking point (2) in the first instance.

The Arrhenius equation :

The equation was developed originally to describe the effect of temperature on the rate of reaction in gas phase or to some extent in liquid phase. The basic tenet of this equation is the formation of an activated complex produced by the free collisions between the reactant molecules and that an equilibrium condition exists between activated and non-activated molecules according to the Boltzman distribution law. In solid state reaction, free movement or rotation of the molecules are usually restricted and the applicability of the Boltzman law has been questioned by Garn⁷¹. However, the similarity between the Eyring's transition state theory and the Arrhenius equation and some successful attempt by Shanon⁷² and Cordes⁷³ to calculate the preexponential factors from statistical thermodynamic point of view suggest

that Arrhenius type of equation can be used in describing the effect of temperature in solid state reaction.

Further it is well established that the Boltzman distribution law forms the basis of the statistical theory of the heat capacity of solids⁷⁴. Therefore, as long as a valid alternative to the Arrhenius equation is not developed, we have to accept it for the sake of mathematical validity to describe the effect of temperature.

Indiscriminate use of models for solid-state reaction :

As it has been stated earlier, the objective of studying kinetics is to elucidate the mechanism of the reaction. In solid state reaction this objective is generally achieved with the help of explicit mathematical models along with the supplementary evidences of identification of various reaction steps. But, the question frequently raised is about the adequacy of these models in the field of heterogeneous kinetics. However, the question itself is purely speculative as to this day no worthy alternative method has been proposed. Therefore, we have no other choice than to assume the adequacy of these models. Since, there are large number of models based on the function $f(\alpha)$, the problem boils down to the selection (discrimination) of the most appropriate model to describe the experimental curve of α versus t . The discrimination methodology followed in isothermal kinetics is the apparently best linear fit of the chosen kinetic model. However, the nature of the models makes it impossible for an unambiguous choice^{69,75}. This is because a model is a mathematical description of an ideal process and therefore, gives an incomplete picture of a real process. A typical example is the decomposition of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ wherein the inference drawn from microscopic observation is different from the best fit model⁷⁶. Consequently, it is commonly observed that several models fit a thermal process equally well which renders any discrimination extremely difficult. In non-isothermal kinetics this problem is still more complex, because the thermoanalytical curves are considerably influenced by several factors which affect the kinetic data derived from TA curves. These are : (i) amount of sample, (ii) change of gaseous environment around the sample, (iii) heating rate, (iv) chemical reaction of the gaseous product with either the intermediate or the product (reversible reaction), (v) particle or grain size of the reactant, (vi) geometry of the sample. All these factors are well-known to the thermoanalytical chemists and have been discussed in detail elsewhere^{62,77-81}. The Arrhenius parameters obtained from the thermoanalytical curves are therefore macroscopic information which are averaged by all these factors leading us to the well-known kinetic compensation effect (KCE) in solid state reactions. This means that any

factor(s) which influences the value of E will automatically influence the value of pre-exponential factor (A) and *vice versa*. This may be expressed mathematically as follows :

$$\ln A = a + bE \quad (91)$$

where, a and b are characteristic constants of the system. Various authors⁸²⁻⁸⁵ have discussed this aspect in more details.

It may be worthwhile to mention here that to obtain kinetic parameters with minimum ambiguity, it is the general consensus of various authors that the following precautions should be taken as much as possible. These are : (i) use of small quantity of sample, (ii) slow heating rate without obscuring different steps of reaction, (iii) both the standard and the sample should be subjected to similar experimental conditions, (iv) gaseous product of decomposition if any, should not be allowed to build up over the reaction surface, (v) isothermal experiment should be carried out at least at three different temperatures to assess the mechanism of the reaction, (vi) same sample size should be used while studying other parameters.

Conclusions :

In conclusions, the author would like to stress that no theory in chemical kinetics is free from certain assumptions and simplifications and therefore cannot answer all the questions regarding different aspects of mechanism, especially of solid state reactions. The kinetic models discussed above give us broad physical picture of the events that takes place during the course of thermally induced reactions. These models cannot provide information on chemical changes/rearrangements of bonds in reactant phase. Many of the methods proposed so far for the determination of Arrhenius parameters have been found to be inadequate when used for TA curves obtained at a single heating rate. However, experimental accuracy is the most important criterion for successful extraction of kinetic parameters.

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References

1. M. E. Brown, D. Dollimore and A. K. Galwey, in "Comprehensive Chemical Kinetics", eds. C. H. Bamford and C. H. F. Tipper, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1980, Vol. 22, p. 6.
2. W. E. Garner (ed.), "Chemistry of the Solid State", Butterworth, London, 1955.
3. J. A. Hedvall, "Solid State Chemistry", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1966.

Kanungo : Kinetics of solid state reactions under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions

4. P. Barret (ed.), "Reaction Kinetics in Heterogeneous Chemical System", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1975.
5. N. D. Hannay (ed.), "Treatise on Solid State Chemistry", Plenum Press, New York, 1976, Vol. 4.
6. C. J. Keatch and D. Dollimore, "An Introduction to Thermogravimetry", 2nd ed. Hayden, London, 1975.
7. J. Sestak, "Thermophysical Properties of Solids. Their Measurements and Theoretical Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
8. J. Sestak, V. Satava and W. W. Wendlandt (eds.), *Thermochim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 333.
9. J. Sestak (ed.), *Thermochim. Acta*, 2002, **23**, 1.
10. W. A. Johnson and K. F. Mehl, *Trans. TMS. AMIE*, 1935, **135**, 416.
11. D. A. Young, "Decomposition of Solids", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1966.
12. J. Simpson, D. Taylor and D. M. W. Anderson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2378.
13. R. A. W. Hill and J. N. Welsh, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 1059.
14. E. G. Prout and F. C. Tompkins, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1944, **40**, 488; 1946, **42**, 482.
15. O. Kubaschewski and B. E. Hopkins, "Oxidation of Metals and Alloys", Butterworth, London, 1962.
16. S. F. Hulbert, *J. Brit. Ceram. Soc.*, 1969, **6**, 11.
17. W. Jander, *Z. Allg. Chem.*, 1927, **163**, 1; *Angew. Chem.*, 1928, **41**, 79.
18. A. M. Ginstling and B. I. Brounshtein, *Zh. Prikl. Khim.*, 1950, **23**, 1327.
19. R. E. Carter, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **34**, 2010.
20. G. Valensi, *Bull. Soc. Chim. (France)*, 1935, **5**, 668.
21. V. F. Zhuravlev, I. G. Lesokhin and R. G. Tempel'man, *J. Appl. Chem., USSR*, 1948, **21**, 887.
22. W. Komatsu, "Reactivity of Solids", Proc. 5th Int Symp., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1965, p.182.
23. J. H. Sharp, G. W. Brindley and B. N. N. Achar, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1966, **49**, 379.
24. E. A. Geiss, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1963, **46**, 374.
25. J. Sestak and G. Berggren, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1971, **3**, 1.
26. V. M. Gorbachev, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1980, **18**, 194.
27. J. Malek and V. Smrcka, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1991, **186**, 153.
28. L. F. Jones, D. Dollimore and T. Nicklin, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1975, **13**, 240.
29. M. E. Brown, A. K. Galwey and A. Li. Wan Po, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **203**, 221.
30. D. Dollimore, J. Dollimore and J. Little, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2496.
31. F. Skvara and V. Satava, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1970, **2**, 325.
32. D. W. Johnson and P. K. Gallagher, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1474.
33. S. B. Kanungo and S. K. Mishra, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1997, **48**, 385.
34. A. E. Newkirk, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 1558.
35. T. R. Ingraham and P. Marier, *Can. J. Chem. Engg.*, 1964, **42**, 161.
36. J. H. Sharp and S. A. Wentworth, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 2060.
37. H. H. Horowitz and G. Metzger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **35**, 1464.
38. G. Gyulai and E. J. Greenhow, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1973, **6**, 254.
39. H. E. Kissinger, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Std.*, 1956, **57**, 217.
40. E. S. Freeman and B. Carroll, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **62**, 394.
41. B. Carroll and E. P. Manche, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1972, **3**, 449.
42. C. D. Doyle, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1970, **5**, 907.
43. C. D. Doyle, *Nature (London)*, 1965, **207**, 290.
44. J. Zsako, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2406.
45. J. Zsako and J. Zsako (Jr.), *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1980, **18**, 333.
46. J. R. MacCallum and J. Tanner, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 1970, **6**, 907.
47. J. M. Criado and A. Ortega, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1984, **80**, 123.
48. K. Madhusudanan, K. Krishnan and K. N. Ninan, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1986, **97**, 189.
49. A. W. Coats and J. P. Redfern, *Nature (London)*, 1964, **201**, 68.
50. E. M. Gobachev, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1975, **8**, 349.
51. M. Balarin, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1977, **12**, 349.
52. C. H. Li, *AIChE. J.*, 1985, **31**, 1036.
53. R. K. Agrawal, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1987, **32**, 149.
54. R. K. Agrawal, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **203**, 93.
55. J. Militky and J. Sestak, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **203**, 31.
56. G. I. Senum and R. T. Yang, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1977, **11**, 445.
57. E. Urbanovici and E. Segal, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1984, **78**, 441; 1985, **91**, 375; 1989, **141**, 9; 1989, **153**, 257; 1990, **159**, 369; 1992, **203**, 153.
58. D. W. van Krevlen, C. van Heerden and F. J. Huntijens, *Fuel*, 1951, **30**, 253.
59. S. R. Dharwadkar and M. D. Kharkhanavala, in "Thermal Analysis", eds. G. F. Schwenker and P. D. Garn. Vol. 3, Academic Press, New York, 1969, p.1049.
60. S. B. Kanungo, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 162.
61. C. D. Doyle, in "Techniques and Methods of Polymer Evaluation", eds. P. E. Slade and L. T. Jenkins, Arnold, London, 1966, Vol. 1, p. 113.
62. J. H. Flynn, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1988, **34**, 367; 1990, **36**, 1579; 1991, **37**, 293.
63. T. Ozawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **38**, 1881; *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1970, **2**, 301.
64. J. H. Flynn and L. A. Wall, *J. Polym. Sci. Part B*, 1966, **4**, 323; *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Std.*, 1966, **A70**, 487.
65. H. Friedman, *J. Polym. Sci., Part C*, 1964, **6**, 183.
66. H. E. Kissinger, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1702.
67. J. P. Elder, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1984, **29**, 1327; 1985, **30**, 657.
68. A. A. Zuru, R. Whitehead and D. L. Griffith, *Thermochim. Acta*,

- 1990, **164**, 285.
69. S. V. Vyazovkin and A. I. Lesnikovich, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1987, **32**, 909; 1989, **35**, 2169.
70. S. V. Vyazovkin and A. I. Lesnikovich, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1990, **165**, 273; 1992, **203**, 177.
71. P. D. Garn, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1978, **13**, 581.
72. R. D. Shanon, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 1902.
73. H. F. Cordes, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 2185.
74. M. C. Reading, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **135**, 37.
75. S. V. Vyazovkin, A. I. Lesnikovich, E. A. Guinin and V. G. Guslev, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **130**, 269.
76. G. G. T. Guarini, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1994, **41**, 287.
77. W. W. Wendlandt, "Thermal Analysis", 3rd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1986.
78. P. D. Garn, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **135**, 71.
79. M. Maciejewski, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1992, **38**, 51.
80. T. P. Prasad, S. B. Kanungo and H. S. Ray, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **203**, 503.
81. H. Tanaka, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1995, **267**, 29.
82. N. Koga and J. Sestak, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1991, **182**, 201.
83. N. Koga and J. Sestak, *J. Thermal Anal.*, 1991, **37**, 1103.
84. N. Koga and J. Sestak, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1991, **185**, 135.
85. H. Tanaka, N. Koga and J. Sestak, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1992, **203**, 203.